

Exploring dilemma games in sustainable urban planning: a Cypriot case study on urban rooftop utilization for climate change

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Abstract. This paper describes the initial stages of a Cypriot case study on urban rooftop utilization for climate change, indicating how games can: foster collaboration; engage citizens; and produce policy incentives through real-world exploration and implications. The focus of the case study is a co-designed serious game developed within the context of the GREAT project (Games Realizing Effective and Affective Transformation) to be utilized as a facilitation tool between citizens and policy makers. Through learning and role-play scenarios, target groups can: voice their attitudes towards climate policies; gain valuable insights into specific initiatives; and enhance their acceptance of green infrastructure and sustainable urban planning. In this paper, we describe the initial co-design stages of the dilemma game, discuss the lessons learned, and provide future directions for research.

1 Introduction

To reach the target of carbon neutrality by 2050, the current climate emergency demands innovative solutions as well as active collaboration between citizens and policymakers. It is imperative that citizens understand and socially embrace sustainable urban planning initiatives [1]. It is equally important that policy makers understand citizens' needs to implement bold initiatives. In response, this paper presents the concept of a co-designed dilemma game to explore rooftop utilization. The game has been designed as a tool for engagement to facilitate constructive dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders. Conducted through a case study methodology pioneered through the GREAT project (Games Realizing Effective and Affective Transformation), it illustrates how games can act as effective communication channels. The GREAT initiative aims to “investigate the potential of digital games and gameplay to engage citizens across Europe through co-design activities to provide input into developing policy priorities on climate change” [2]. Furthermore, GREAT intends to demonstrate the positive impact of games on social engagement and dialogue by allowing citizens to express preferences and attitudes on policy dilemmas related to climate change.

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In this paper, we present the initial stages of a case study undertaken in collaboration with the NGO Urban Gorillas in Nicosia, Cyprus. As a member of the European Creative Rooftop Network (ECRN), a project co-funded by the CREATIVE EUROPE funding programme. Urban Gorillas identified rooftop utilization as a policy dilemma to be explored through the GREAT methodology resulting in the development of a dilemma game which engages citizens and stakeholders in learning and role-playing scenarios. More specifically, the game presents real-world implications of green rooftop utilization, covering benefits and opportunities for stakeholders in tackling climate change as well as challenges and barriers to green roof implementation and incentive schemes to counteract foreseen challenges. Through interactive face-to-face game sessions, participants explore solutions that address the needs and concerns of all parties involved. Within the game, players have the chance to understand a green initiative which works towards social acceptance of a sustainable urban planning practice in the context of green infrastructure.

Initial outcomes suggest benefits for policy incentives, demonstrating that the games-based methodology effectively: engaged participants; fostered meaningful dialogue and collaboration; enhanced understanding of rooftop utilization's potential for sustainability; and increased citizen participation in urban planning discussions.

The European Environment Agency [1] advocates for further engagement with citizens, especially in relation to green infrastructure policy and decision-making processes which need to be discussed from the outset. Public consultation is a well-established practice in Urban Planning, yet there is debate that conventional tools no longer provide meaningful dialogue. One solution to meet the needs of contemporary society is playful media culture which has the potential to advance creativity and to address citizen engagement [3]. The project leverages the potential of games to influence policy making and as advocated by Wamsler, et al [4], the need for citizen involvement to increase relevance, fairness, acceptance, and, ultimately, sustainability.

It is anticipated that through further citizen and stakeholder engagement in future game sessions, we will encourage: improved communication between citizens and policymakers; and the generation of innovative policy recommendations tailored to local needs. The methodology applied in the GREAT project is designed to be adapted to various policy dilemmas addressing the climate crisis beyond rooftop utilization and the scope of this paper. Policymakers and policy stakeholders can repeat the cycle to explore diverse policy issues and dilemmas relating to climate change and beyond, gaining valuable insights. More specifically, it is a methodology that has the potential to increase citizens' acceptance of green infrastructure and sustainable urban planning.

This paper is divided into the following sections. Section 2 presents urban rooftop utilization and dilemma-based serious games in urban planning. Section 3 presents the Research Methodology. Section 4 presents the implementation of the dilemma game for rooftop utilization. Section 5 details findings gained during the game, evaluation of findings and policy insights. Section 6 provides discussions and conclusions.

2 Urban Rooftop Utilization and Dilemma Serious Games

The UN [5] has predicted that by 2050, 68% of the world's population will be living in cities. Demands on cities continue to grow, and globally, political decision-makers are in search of ways to tackle the climate crisis as well as challenges in climate resistance and energy consumption. There appears to be an overall acceptance that we are experiencing the climate crisis, yet public awareness and its effects were widely underestimated in the past [6]. Today, most Europeans recognize climate change as one of the most serious problems facing the

world. There has been a significant increase in general climate change awareness in the global population [7]. Furthermore, there has been an immense number of climate protests such as the 'Fridays for Future' movement which brings public attention to the issues at hand. A recent study into the 2019 London Extinction Rebellion [8], (the first attempt to create large-scale disruption in west London) noted that the rebellion was a success in strengthening general environment attitudes, but nevertheless it did not lead to major growth or improved environmental policy. In relation to these findings, awareness of climate change among the population however does not necessarily translate into effective behavioural changes to protect the environment [9]. More efforts are required to be undertaken both by citizens and policy makers to protect the climate. Furthermore, being aware of climate change does not necessarily imply that citizens have sufficient knowledge relating to policies that can counteract climate impacts. Citizens require more knowledge about effective policies in order to voice their preferences, including areas such as mobility, food, or housing, while in parallel, there are no effective communication channels between policy makers and citizens for a huge number of the global population especially those who do not vote, cannot vote, or do not know how to vote [10].

According to the World Economic Forum [11], housing is the frontline in the fight against climate change and investing in sustainable housing is a win-win situation. Not only should housing be adequate, safe and sustainable to protect against adverse climate impacts such as extreme heat, floods, storms, there must be adaptation solutions making use of housing products and technologies which are less carbon-intensive than traditional materials. Yet, *"too many investors lack awareness of the many opportunities to address sustainable housing needs of millions of families"* [11]. Cities worldwide are a major concern for sustainable living and carbon emissions, particularly, the large spread of concrete buildings that do not allow affordances for greenery to be fostered. 15 years ago, the GRACC project [6], advocated that local authorities need more control over planning departments to reduce the impact, one such initiative was Green Roofs. Rooftop utilization, or the rooftop as the fifth façade [12], has gained great significance over the past years. The utilization of both green roofs and walls are a part of green infrastructure which promote a more sustainable and efficient development [13], taking advantage of reduction of island heat and improvement in air and health quality. There are currently examples of good practices in rooftop policies: Zürich's green roof programme 1991; Basels Building and Construction Law 2002; Munich's Green Roof Ordinance, 1997; Copenhagen's Green Roof Policy 2010; and France's commercial buildings by law to partially have their roofs covered with plants or solar panels, 2015 [14].

A recent study by Adilkhanova et, al. [15] concluded from simulations that if implemented across cities as a 90% coverage, Green Roofs have the potential to lower energy consumption by 7.7% as well as lowering the temperature (air and surface) by 0.54 °C and 2.17 °C, respectively. Furthermore, green roofs can increase absorption of CO₂ and provide the added benefit of improved aesthetics of the city. It must be noted that this paper does not aim to discuss the technicalities of green roofs; vast publications are available, for an overview please refer to [15-28].

In order to promote active collaboration between citizens and policy makers in green urban planning, could serious games be an answer? Over the past decade, serious games have been established as a method of co-design [29, 30], but many of these are employed during the design process and not at the initial consultation stages [31]. Additionally, a continuous problem is the one-way flow of information, from officials to citizens [32, 33]: there is little engagement in localized knowledge in order to define opportunities or problems from the citizens' perspective. Furthermore, conventional methods do not allow affordances for citizens to 'take action' to address specific policies [34]. Through co-creative methods,

participants can play active roles, yet this is most traditionally linked to temporary interventions and movements like DIY Urbanism [35] or Tactical Urbanism [36]. In addition, if the participant does not fully understand the participatory method they are involved in, as well as the bigger picture and long-term goal of an urban design policy, they will not be able to fully participate and unfortunately, their voice will not be heard [31].

3 Research Methodology

The research question underpinning the initial steps of the case study displayed in this paper is: *How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?*

This study utilizes the GREAT case study methodology [37] which implements co-design processes involving policy stakeholders and citizens. Thus, this methodology also provides a link between policy and the public.

Table 1. Steps in the GREAT Project Methodology

Step 1: <i>What the case study will achieve and with whom</i>	Participating stakeholders will join a workshop or equivalent activities to identify and prioritize the research topics.
Step 2: <i>Game activity concepts</i>	Participating stakeholders will join a workshop or equivalent activities to generate ideas for the game activity.
Step 3: <i>Collaborative design of game activities</i>	Participating stakeholders will engage in activities to co-create a story, the narrative for a DIBL serious game.
Step 4: <i>Games activities with case study participants</i>	Games-based activities with case study participants are carried out.
Step 5: <i>Collaborative data analysis</i>	Participating stakeholders will participate in a workshop or similar collaborative activities to interpret the data obtained from games activities.
Step 6: <i>Policy conclusions & evaluation</i>	Collaboratively formulate the conclusions that can be drawn from the results of Step 5.
Step 7: <i>Community engagement</i>	Promote community engagement activities that are impacted by the policy dilemma and identify dissemination opportunities.
Step 8: <i>Policy stakeholder engagement</i>	Close the cycle by engaging with policy stakeholders, and in particular the policymakers who identified the dilemma addressed by the case study.

The GREAT case study methodology [38] follows an eight-step process, each stage providing details for co-design and implementation. The work presented in this paper focuses on step 4, the remaining steps of the case study which are beyond the scope of this paper will inevitably close the loop on the cycle in future research, through detailed policy insights, policy stakeholder dissemination and the presentation of results directly to policy makers, the purpose of each step is listed in Table 1.

The project objectives and steps in the cycle determine the types of activities and participants to be involved in the co-design processes, i.e. citizens, domain experts, policy stakeholders and policymakers etc. The following section outlines the steps of the methodology in relation to the rooftop utilization case study.

3.1 Case Study: Re-utilization of Urban Rooftops in Nicosia

In this paper, we explore the initial stages of a GREAT case study through working with an organization that had a clear pre-existing environmental mission exploring a climate change emergency through a localized dilemma. The Case Study is sponsored by a non-profit organization called Urban Gorillas who are based in Nicosia, Cyprus. Urban Gorillas have extensive knowledge in Urban Planning, envisioning socially inclusive cities which are sustainable, healthy and creative.

According to the European Environment Agency [39], Europe is among the most forested regions of the world, around 40% of its land area is covered by forests. Yet, in 2021, the capital city of Nicosia, Cyprus had the lowest percentage of Urban Tree coverage in Europe at just 4% [40].

Despite the low statistics, Cyprus continues to fill its empty plots within its cities with construction sites rather than green solutions. Between January 2022 and March 2023, over 160 new apartment buildings were initiated [41] and between March 2023 and March 2024, this increased to 541, 165 specifically in Nicosia [42].

Urban Gorillas are members of the European Creative Rooftop Network (ECRN), a network which spans nine European cities, promoting the creative use of rooftops to address urban challenges [43]. Urban Gorillas identified rooftop utilization as a localized policy dilemma to be explored through the GREAT methodology, allowing games to facilitate discussions on the utilization of urban rooftops and the future possibilities of such initiatives, especially in the context of the boom in construction during recent years and the abundance of flat rooftops available within the Capital City of Nicosia. Urban Gorillas noted that there are currently a few examples of green roof implementation in the city of Nicosia: the A.G Leventis Gallery, the University of Cyprus library; and some privately owned houses.

Fig.1. CEA Green Roof, Nicosia, Cyprus

Furthermore, the Cyprus Energy Agency (CEA) implemented a green roof in 2023 (See figure 1), being the first mixed use building to implement such a project on a building consisting of multiple apartments and offices, paving the way in increasing local knowledge and good practices in green roofs in the Cypriot context. Recent data retrieved from the site has demonstrated the effect the roof has on surface temperature in the Cypriot Context as seen in figure 2.

Fig.2. Surface temperature of the CEA Green Roof, Nicosia, Cyprus, Thursday June 6th 2024, Air Temperature 45 degrees Celsius.

More specifically, Urban Gorillas and ECRN promote the ‘Rainbow Rooftop’ Policy [44] where rooftops are categorized by colour thus defining their usage as seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Rainbow Roof Top Policy [44]

Green	Green rooftops used to provide green space, increase biodiversity in the city and reduction of urban heat effect
Blue	Blue: rooftops used to collect and store (rain) water and ensure delayed drainage
Yellow	Yellow: rooftops used to generate sustainable and renewable energy
Red	Red: rooftops used as meeting spaces with social functions such as culture, sports or recreation, that promote social cohesion
Orange	Orange: rooftops used for urban mobility purposes
Purple	Purple: rooftops used for vertical densification by adding new volumes (mostly residential, but not exclusively)
Grey	Grey: rooftops used for technical functions, such as installations and utility services

The case study leverages the network's expertise to create urban spaces focused on inclusion, co-creation and sustainability initiatives aiming to drive change in the way buildings are designed as well as how the utilization of currently ‘lost’ spaces of the city can be reclaimed in the context of the climate emergency. Linking to current literature Roggero [45] suggests that *“Local governments looking for guidance should not simply establish contacts and exchange good practices [...] they should rather reach out to those cities that have the same type of installations. [...] This way, cities will learn about green roof policies that address the specific social dilemmas at play in their respective jurisdictions”*. As such, leveraging expertise from an organization linked to 8 other European cities, some of whom already exhibit good practice in rooftop utilization, provides the case study with invaluable insight and data from the onset.

Following the GREAT case study methodology, steps 1 and 2 were completed through the identification of the rooftop utilization policy dilemma, as detailed further in Yau et, al [46]. Subsequently, the case study lead, Frederick University and Urban Gorillas began stage 3: the co-design of a Dilemma game. Partner in the GREAT project Serious Games Interactive (SGI), produce collaborative games through Dilemma Based Learning (DiBL). DiBL is a proprietary platform producing dilemma-based learning games that enable engaging and inclusive facilitator-driven offline or online collaborative experiences. Utilizing DiBL in this case study employs a serious game to gain qualitative data, which also supports any quantitative data collected. The end-user experience in a DiBL game is a format consisting of a game screen for the facilitator, as seen in figure 3, where the game progression is controlled, shared game content is shown, and the effect of participant decisions is recorded. There is also a separate game screen for each participant, where they will receive participant-specific information and make choices on their mobile devices [47].

Fig. 3. The combination of DiBL with facilitator screen and mobile phone [48]

As part of the GREAT methodology, dilemma games fulfill an educational role by providing participants with learning experiences about different actions and consequences regarding climate policies, in this case, rooftop utilization.

The co-design of the dilemma game began with a wireframe which visualized the content and game flow, which would be designed and then transferred into a working prototype in the DiBL platform. In collaboration with Urban Gorillas, it was decided that the game would include real-world implications of green rooftop utilization, covering aspects such as: benefits and opportunities of rooftop utilization; challenges and barriers to implementation; incentives and fairness considerations; as well as potential policy solutions and stakeholder perspectives. Although there is the potential to hold game sessions online, it was concluded that face-to-face game sessions were more appropriate to such a localized case study and for better collaboration in group discussions. Furthermore, it was decided that:

- 3 DiBL sessions should be designed with separate information sets depending on the target group: Citizens/Investors/Architects
- Sessions should include a minimum of 8 persons and a maximum of 16 persons to better facilitate the discussions
- A roleplay element should be included as a method to induce perspective-taking
- Professional standard visuals should be developed for the game (images & videos) to entice participants

- Due to the complex dilemma and length of the game, it was determined that the game should be held in 2 parts to allow the participants a short break in-between.

Part 1 would: include a video presentation demonstrating the rainbow rooftop policy and all of the benefits of rooftop utilization; present various stakeholder perspectives, introducing participants to stakeholders such as the building manager, different resident groups, and the investor; Display potential challenges around safety, accessibility, maintenance, costs etc; Promote potential incentives to counteract these challenges; Allow participants to suggest their own incentives; and lastly to discuss the fairness of such incentives.

Part 2 would: present specific localized dilemmas within the context of rooftop utilization placing participants into groups where they would assume a character role opposite to themselves. Furthermore, the game would: include a debate section where groups would discuss and negotiate in order to try to convince each other of their incentive preferences; and include a vote for policy incentives aiming for an overall consensus fair to all stakeholders involved. The process would then be repeated with a second dilemma allowing participants to stay in character and develop their views from another perspective.

Linking back to the literature area, the overall aim was to leverage the possibilities of the game for participants to learn the potentials of rooftop utilization to increase relevance; fairness; acceptance; and, ultimately, sustainability attitudes [49].

By exploring a range of solutions addressing all stakeholders involved, players would have the opportunity to understand the green initiative which works towards social acceptance of a relatively unknown sustainable urban planning practice and green infrastructure in the Cypriot context.

Fig. 4. Partial wireframe for game content and flow

Once the wireframe was designed (see partial example in figure 4) and the question sets were decided in collaboration with Urban Gorillas, the case study lead worked in collaboration with SGI to produce the visuals for the game, the game flow was created within the DiBL platform (figure 5) and internally tested.

Data would be collected during the event and analyzed post-event. Data was collected via:

- Open-ended discussion questions at the end of the session
- Participant feedback forms
- Recorded audio transcript of the sessions
- Participant choices during game play (recorded through the quiz and branching options of DiBL and presented as excel data post-game)

Data would allow the researchers to evaluate game-play and to address the research question: *How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?*

Fig. 5. DiBL Facilitator and Participant Screen

4 Game Implementation

The following section presents step 4 of the GREAT research cycle: the face-to-face facilitation of games activities with case study participants.

The first game session took place with 9 active participants, 1 facilitator and 1 observer (see figures 6 & 7). Participants were recruited through Frederick University and Urban Gorillas. Participants encompassed a range of ages from 20-74, as well as diverse occupations, all participants were currently living in or had recently lived in an apartment block. The sessions in the dilemma game last approximately three hours, including a break between parts 1 and 2.

Part 1 began with a short introduction to the GREAT project. Participants were then asked to introduce themselves as an ice breaking activity. To join the game, participants were provided with a QR code (figure 6) to access the session via their mobile devices. Once participants joined, they were shown the introductory video (figure 7) on the facilitation screen about the potential benefits and positives of green roofs based on the rainbow rooftop policy recommendations [44], prompting initial discussions and reactions from the participants.

Fig. 6. Introducing DiBL to Participants

Fig. 7. Introductory video display

The game included a vote on whether players felt the green roof initiative would be a positive move for the city, the results remained secret and could only be viewed by the researchers

post-game. It was determined during the game design that players may be influenced by the result of the vote and this would affect game play.

The next step was the introduction to key stakeholders, players were asked to vote on who they would like to talk to, to understand the challenges that certain societal groups may face if such an initiative was implemented. By providing multiple stakeholder options, participants were able to better understand the potential issues and concerns of the policy dilemma. In this version of the game, players could decide between the: building manager; top-floor residents; parents with children; and senior citizens. This was done through a voting system on their mobile device. Players quickly realized that there were potential challenges around maintenance, safety, accessibility, privacy, and community dynamics and decided that they should talk to all available parties.

As the participants gained more knowledge in the challenges faced by certain groups, discussions progressed, participants were then provided with potential incentives for the specific characters displayed. Crucially to the research and the policy dilemma, the next stage prompted participants to suggest their own incentives and support mechanisms which policy makers could provide to alleviate potential challenges.

The overall nature of part 1 was exploratory, it allowed participants to establish context with the policy dilemma and to learn about rooftop utilization within a local context. Essentially, part 1 provided the learning tools required to understand the policy dilemma and the backdrop to the roleplay dilemmas presented in part 2.

Part 2 began by placing participants into groups of 2 or 3 and assigning different roles to each group. Roles included: the private investor; the building manager; and resident groups (first-floor, top-floor, etc.). Each group was provided with photographs of an existing building; individual tailored documents outlining their position in the building and a brief profile specific to each role. Participants did not know each other's roles until they were presented to the group. During the DiBL session, the participants' mobile device screen shared information regarding the themes each role would consider, i.e. safety; access; common expenses; privacy; exclusivity. The aim was for groups to take on roles opposite to their own characters in order to develop and expand on the provided profiles which would then be presented to the group.

Once the roles were established, two core dilemmas were presented: 1) the building owner would respond to the new policy by installing a green roof on the perimeter of the building and solar panels in the center, this would restrict access to the rooftop to residents (all residents were tenants renting the apartments). Furthermore, they would not have access to the electricity generated, it would be sold for the profit of the owner; and 2) the participants' building had been chosen as a pilot initiative for a green roof policy to be funded and implemented by the local authorities at no initial cost to the residents.

The groups were asked to engage in discussions to determine their key priorities and concerns one dilemma at a time. They presented their arguments to the group and in turn attempted to convince one another of their preferred incentives. Furthermore, participants were reminded that to achieve a mutually beneficial outcome, they must consider the views of others. They then voted on the fairest outcome and once the results were shown, they discussed the level of fairness.

5 Findings

The findings presented in this section are a combination of the analysis of the audio transcript of the game session, participants choices during game play and feedback forms.

Following the video demonstration of the positives of rooftop utilization, participants were asked to note the benefits they could envision for tenants/owners of apartments for the

city of Nicosia. A variety of answers were collected, the most common connection was the benefit of extra space and a means to be closer to nature. There was then a secret vote to assess the positivity level of participants to the proposed policy. Findings revealed that 50% were ‘very negative’, 10% were ‘negative’ and 40% were ‘somewhat positive’, ‘positive’ and ‘extremely positive’ secured no votes.

A notable perspective was the first choice of stakeholder whom participants voted to speak to. 87% chose the ‘building manager’, justifying their choice as ‘the building manager is the one who takes action for the building and is the one who would be in charge of the roof space’, as such this held more meaning than the residents in the first instance.

Fig. 8. Participants concerns of rooftop utilization

Fig. 9. Perceived challenges of rooftop utilization

Feedback from participants showed that they agreed with the challenges presented. Voting on the most important concerns, findings revealed that ‘long term sustainability’ was the greatest barrier with 40% of the vote, ‘safety concerns’ 30% (figure 8), whereas ‘child-friendly design’, ‘accessibility concerns’ and ‘tenant engagement and cooperation’ scored only 10% respectively.

Additional challenges were discussed and identified; players interacted with their mobile devices to input free text. Challenges identified were issues of: cleaning; access; humidity; maintenance; respect of the shared space; weather; who manages the rooftop; noise disturbance; and if the residents in fact wanted to use the roof.

Participants then voted on the answers, in agreement with the previous vote, results showed ‘maintenance’ was identified as the main challenge. Results additionally showed social aspects beginning to arise with the ‘respect of shared space’ and ‘access for all’ being identified as issues of concern (figure 9).

Although ‘maintenance’ and ‘long-term sustainability’ were voted as main barriers to rooftop utilization, the following vote on incentives to address residents' concerns showed that ‘child friendly design grants’ and ‘financial assistance programs’ were prioritized (figure 10).

Further game play identified unfair scenarios for residents. First, cleaning problems, what would happen if someone had a party on the roof and didn't clean up and secondly will apartments cost more, both to buy and to rent? Others concentrated on finances, and the issue of compensation, questioning if some people would get more, less or differential treatment? A further major concern was, ‘if the government did provide grants for such initiatives, would the money be given before or after the implementation’, as currently with other green initiatives (such as solar panel installation) grant requests are submitted post installation and citizens have been waiting months to receive the grant.

Fig. 10. Potential incentives to address concerns of rooftop utilization

Also, within the discussion of grants, there was the suggestion that to be fair, they need tight control of the usage to minimize the misuse of funds. Lastly, participants recognized the need for the new legislation to include eco or sustainable materials as a requirement in the design and building process of the rooftops, not merely the installation of plants, to enhance the climate change initiative. Overall, at this point in the findings, participants expressed the view that the policy was too challenging for existing buildings, but it would work well with new buildings.

Fig. 11. Potential incentives to address concerns of rooftop utilization (Dilemma 1)

Fig. 12. Potential incentives to address concerns of rooftop utilization (Dilemma 2)

During the role play exercise in part 2, participants voted for the best incentive in relation to the localized dilemmas presented to them. Dilemma 1 was the scenario of the building owner implementing the policy for their own financial gain. Within this dilemma, participants voted in their roles. Findings revealed that only 2 from the 8 given incentives were chosen. These were ‘financial compensation’ (66%) and ‘tenant amenities and energy efficiency support’ (34%) (Figure 11).

Dilemma 2 placed participants in a scenario where their building was chosen as a pilot initiative for the green roof policy. Findings showed that participants viewed this scenario fairer than the first dilemma yet, the top floor owner felt at a disadvantage due to the inconvenience they would receive, i.e noise and disturbance. As a result, findings reveal that the players were less inclined towards the financial incentives within this scenario voting in favour of ‘community engagement initiatives’ (44%), as a means to inform and educate the public (figure 12).

To find equitable solutions, participants suggested that the disadvantaged parties, i.e. the top floor residents in dilemma 2, should be granted either: a discounted rent; exemption from the common expenses, or reduced priced apartments on the top floor.

The last two questions focused on the roleplay approach. Findings revealed that 63% believed their opinion changed when their role did (figure 13), and 75% of participants believed their opinion on fairness had changed now they had been in the position of someone else (figure 14).

Fig. 13. Opinions related to the roleplay approach

Fig. 14. Opinions related to the roleplay approach and fairness perception.

Data collected in the post-game discussion and feedback form revealed that all participants thought that the DiBL session was engaging, stating that the ‘game was for all’, ‘the role play and mobile device interaction was engaging’ as well as ‘observing the positive interactions between fellow participants’. In collaboration with the findings in figure 13, participant feedback revealed that most preferred playing someone else, with 75% stating that they were able to view the dilemma from another point of view, the overall consensus was that ‘when you had to think what others would say it made you more aware of how others think and feel.’ Furthermore, all participants felt the sessions allowed for diverging opinions.

5.1 Evaluation of Findings

The initial results of the secret vote took a negative perspective towards a green roof policy, which can be translated as policy hesitations. Upon further analysis from participant debriefing, participants noted that they were not negative to the social aspects of green roofs, but they highlighted concerns for the importance of proper planning and technical solutions. Most importantly they perceived low level of workmanship in Cyprus as a major concern, noting leakage and structural damage as main concerns. Despite the initial negativity, participants were observed as remaining positive about their participation during the game process.

They highlighted many social and environmental advantages to the policy including the benefit of additional usable areas and the opportunity to connect with nature. As such, participants appreciated the concept of the green roof initiative, however, they did highlight their concerns regarding feasibility and implementation challenges. The negativity displayed goes hand in hand with the concerns relating to feasibility as well as the practical implementation, especially in older buildings with pre-existing residents.

Regarding the choice of the building manager as the first point of contact highlights the importance of the role of the management company in the implementation of the policy at the individual building level. This would require the building manager to take a mediating role in policy implementation, yet this was perceived as a concern of the manager role in relation to workload and extra financial burden, providing adequate resources has the potential to mitigate these issues.

Findings highlighted that differential treatment provides further barriers to the acceptance of a green roof policy. Participants stressed the unfair advantages of certain groups which a flexible incentive structure could mitigate, as well as clear communication channels. Towards the end of the session, participants were asked what they had learnt from the game play in relation to the policy dilemmas and its incentives. Answers included: ‘Someone will be unhappy even though you provide them a lot’; ‘people will want what’s best for them and it does not mean that it will match all opinions’; ‘you cannot please

everyone of course'; 'each group has a different perspective and you can't please each group.' Most of the submitted answers expressed similar opinions, even if they were articulated differently. One participant noted that: 'initial options are not always the most workable and beneficial, they would like the freedom to choose.' This opinion suggests the need for flexible incentives which could be chosen by different stakeholders, there is no one-size fits all solution. The last opinion noted 'let's be willing to work together and think collectively and not by personal benefits,' highlighting the importance of collective action to enhance policy acceptance. Providing knowledge in climate change initiatives allowed participants to be more accepting of the green infrastructure proposition despite the challenges presented.

The roleplay format was a valuable method of eliciting greater stakeholder perspectives, both the participants and the researchers noted that this was crucial to the study as we did not receive just a one-dimensional response. It allowed participants to hear and consider viewpoints from different stakeholder groups other than their own. Findings revealed that all participants felt that they had participated equally and had learnt new perspectives and ideas, not merely on the subject of green roofs but in the difficulty of the implementation of green initiatives.

It must be noted that during the role play activity, the participants thought critically, took on board the perspectives of their character as well as the positions of others. Participants were able to listen to different viewpoints, and positively engaged in problem-solving, even if they did not find a perfect consensus at the end. Game play allowed participants to consider the complexity and implications of the policy dilemma, and most vitally it provided a means to be much more than a one-way flow of information [33].

5.2 Policy Insights

Insights from the fourth step of the case study indicate that implementing a green roof policy in Cyprus would face significant challenges, mostly in balancing diverse needs as well as concerns of the different stakeholder groups, especially in an existing building context.

Concerns ranged from long term sustainability, safety, access, direct costs to owners and tenants, noise disturbances, as well as privacy. This indicated how complex policy implementation would be to satisfy all residents. Fair as well as effective incentives across various stakeholders and different building types should be carefully considered. Overall, there was a great struggle in finding solutions that would not be unfair. As suggested by our participants, flexible incentives could satisfy more groups, and educating these groups was crucial for success and understanding.

Findings showed that integrating green roof initiatives would be feasible and greatly supported in new buildings, most importantly if they can be planned upfront and included in the building's amenities from the outset so that the tenants and owners would buy into the initiative without disruption. Retrofitting existing buildings comes with a higher cost, a large number of constraints and in some cases may face legal issues due to ownership and long-term sustainability. Yet, an abundance of empty roof spaces exists in Cyprus which should not discourage policy implementation, especially due to the long-term payoff of enhanced advantages for old buildings in terms of energy efficiency [50].

Essentially, effective communication channels should be designed and adopted for ease of collaboration between residents, building managers and owners to ease the burden from the building managers and to avoid rising costs based on the increased workload of the building managers and specific needs for the roof's long-term maintenance.

Outcomes also provided the perspective of considering the local cultural context as well as the norms around living in a communal building in the Cypriot context. With the right practical support to the initiative a green roof policy could be more acceptable to the residents especially if focus is made on feasibility, costs and practical benefits such as long-term

sustainability support. More specifically, at this early stage of the research, the main policy insights surround:

- Equity and Fairness in incentives. Incentives should include guidelines and regulations to prevent any misuse in maximizing income.
- Incentives should be structured as to provide support to the underserved members of the community and to promote social equity.
- Promoting and rewarding long-term sustainability will ensure ongoing benefits.
- Safety and Accessibility. Ensuring all green roofs are safe and accessible is beneficial to all residents.
- Financial Compensation, such as subsidies, rent discounts and reduction in common expenses should be available to disadvantaged residents.
- Market Differentiation, to increase property value through 'green building' certificates would incentivize owners and investors.
- Training and Skill Development, for building managers and investors as well as targeted incentive programs would provide better support to successfully implement and sustain the initiative.
- The integration of sustainable materials, water harvesting systems, urban agriculture and recreational spaces have the potential to support a variety of uses simultaneously.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a serious dilemma game approach within the context of a policy dilemma surrounding rooftop utilization. As a tool for collecting and analyzing citizens' attitudes, it also served as a method for learning about a specific action relating to urban planning within the context of the climate emergency in a localized environment. Within the stages of game development and implementation we involved policy stakeholders and citizens, both of which will have significant influence on the future direction of the case study. With both groups we will implement: further sessions; evaluation workshops; and dissemination events.

Prior to implementing the dilemma game, researchers questioned: *How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?* Although at an early stage in the research cycle, the insights gained from the session have demonstrated positive implementation of a serious dilemma game which: promoted a sustainable initiative, actively engaged the participants, and allowed them to learn from and be part of an innovative means of sustainable urban planning consultation. Most crucially promoting two-way knowledge transfer. In this case, participants also felt they gained significantly from the session.

The session displayed in this paper elicited both quantitative and qualitative results through the in-depth nature of the session as well as through the player choices throughout the game, allowing the researchers to collect meaningful incentives to be transferred to policy makers. By following the first 4 steps of the GREAT case study methodology, we were able to develop a complex serious dilemma game that can be utilized as a mediation tool between citizens and policy makers. The development of the dilemma game provides citizens the opportunity to; voice their attitudes towards a climate policy; gain valuable insights into specific initiatives; and enhance their acceptance of green infrastructure and sustainable urban planning. In order for city wide acceptance, the fostering of a collaborative environment can work towards building more inclusive cities. Participants strongly highlighted that the game process allowed them to engage in a deeper understanding of the green roof initiative through the presented dilemmas, thus bringing participants into closer contact with the policy initiative. Furthermore, the approach of a serious dilemma game has

the potential to invite participants who would not usually engage in traditional urban planning consultation, thus bringing new voices to the table in future sessions, i.e. youth, low-income residents, and other underrepresented members of the community.

Linking back to literature findings, engaging communities in the co-design and decision-making process, in particular lower-income residents begins to work towards the most vulnerable in terms of cost burden [51], which goes hand in hand with wider acceptance of green infrastructure initiatives, thus building trust through a transparent process [52] is of utmost importance. Engaging a variety of stakeholders from different positions is always a challenge, especially in the acceptance of green infrastructure, as it proves hard to engage with them all at the same time. Through the serious game approach, we demonstrate a method that removes hierarchy, bringing them together on ‘an even playing field.’ This approach provides a platform for underrepresented members of the community to voice their opinions, which translates into greater depth of policy insights to be transferred directly to policy makers. One particular policy insight highlighted within this study is: *“Incentives should be structured as to provide support to the underserved members of the community and to promote social equity”*. The need for flexible policy design is essential to assess the needs of each individual group, considering renters, lower-income groups, and those in more challenging buildings. In line with the pilot findings demonstrated in this paper, as well as the current literature, tax breaks, subsidies for maintenance costs, or community grants for collective rooftop gardening initiatives are crucial. [53].

It is essential to highlight that rooftop utilisation is highly contextual based on the scenario of each rooftop, i.e. new or old structure, one owner or multiple owners, profile of residents etc. As a result, and in addition to flexible policy design, the study has shown that incentives need to be provided on a case by case basis to assess the needs of: collective maintenance; reducing individual costs; and fostering community engagement. The next stages of the project will continue to implement further sessions with citizens to elicit further insights, as well as alternative sessions with a second group including Architects, Engineers, Urban Planners and Designers, and a third group including Building Owners, Investors, Builders, Developers and Contractors.

Furthermore, the GREAT project's methodology can be adapted to various climate challenges and policy dilemmas beyond rooftop utilization. The GREAT project will implement a minimum of 10 case studies focusing on policy dilemmas in the context of the climate emergency within its three-year lifespan, in order to provide a methodology which allows policymakers to replicate the format. This will allow policymakers to explore diverse policy issues with different target groups, gaining valuable insights and in this case enhancing citizens' acceptance to green infrastructure and sustainable urban planning and beyond.

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Data availability statement: A full dataset is not currently available as the case study cycle is still in progress and collecting further data. The data that support the findings of this paper are available from

the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The full data set will be available through: <https://www.greatproject.gg/> once the case study is complete.

Author contributions: The first and second author conceptualized the case study. Additionally, the first author conducted the case study and analyzed the data. All authors reviewed the case study development and its findings. The third author supported the writing and revision of the manuscript.

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